

From Code to Collaboration: Role of AI in Shaping Organisational Culture

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When working with scientific data, there are fundamental principles that everyone agrees on: standardisation, integration capabilities, data reusability, transparency, interoperability, and long-term data accessibility. Current data practices and their use in AI technologies are further changing the way data is analysed and managed. Practitioners are keen to break down silos, work together in a more interdisciplinary manner, share good working practices, and standardise tools that lead to reproducible outcomes. A greater need for collaboration is being expressed across all levels of the organisation, including the business teams and those developing specific data and AI tools.

But how do we achieve all of this? And how, especially, do we achieve it in an organisation comprising specialists across a range of scientific disciplines, delivering a range of technical solutions for varying sectors in countries around the world? As a UK government agency seeking to tackle some of the world’s most urgent environmental problems, Cefas (the Centre for Environment, Fisheries and Aquaculture Science) is an example of an organisation grappling with exactly those questions.

Joseph Ribeiro, a fisheries data scientist at Cefas for almost a decade, and Expert-in-Residence (EiR) in *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub, says: “Discussions with other practitioners suggest that it is often tricky to align working practices across teams and there is no silver bullet. Especially in data science and AI organisations, it requires iterative work, vigilance, and experienced management processes built around data to inform organisational strategies.”

Reflecting on this challenge in the context of Cefas, Joseph has developed this case study as a means of understanding alignment. “Investigating whether there was a carrot that might encourage people to choose to align their work, and to work in a more homogenous way. I’d favour that over a stick, be that a rule, restriction, guidelines or new procedure to follow.”, adds Joseph, “If people are storing their code in repositories, and better still, if they are doing so in a public repository, that is something that should be celebrated. If people are working in similar research areas, but never collaborate, it would be great to connect those people.”

Organisational Practices Need to Evolve with AI

Given the advances of text-generative large language models (LLMs), dozens of resumes and Curriculum Vitae (CVs) can now be generated at the click of a button – a rising frustration to those involved on either side of the organisational recruitment process. A Turing Way Practitioners Hub session led

by expert in residence Sophie Carr from Bays Consulting discussed ethical fairness in CV screening. While this discussion mostly addressed screening CVs with algorithms, a supplementary question was posed, “What is better than a CV?”, highlighting the need to evolve organisational practices with AI. Joseph says: “The group agreed that while it depends on the role, version-controlled repositories like GitHub offer valuable insights in AI and data science, serving as a reliable ground-truth source when available. Although making work public is somewhat of a luxury, if a candidate has used GitHub, it offers a useful window into their skills and expertise by showcasing their previous work.”

Reviewing the historic code written by a job applicant can provide insights into their technical expertise as well as their working habits, such as the implementation of coding standards, problem-solving skills, and attention to detail. Cross-institutional platforms like GitHub can also evidence involvement in various projects and the ability to work efficiently, asynchronously and collaboratively, and contribute meaningfully to team efforts.” To answer this, Joseph and colleagues have taken a retrospective look at his use of GitHub over the past decade.

Lessons from Exploring Organisational Use of GitHub

Cefas adopted GitHub for transparency and reproducibility through collaborative GitHub repositories. In doing so, Cefas has also generated a wealth of organisational data that could now be explored for valuable insights. Using algorithms and AI tools, GitHub data can provide insights into how the work culture has evolved.

At the start of this journey, Joseph used the data collected from Cefas's GitHub Organisation, both from within the organisation (authenticated) and to gain an external point of view. Furthermore, he looked at how presenting these insights might communicate and credit contributions made by staff members, incentivising them to adopt practices to “do it right”.

Joseph adds: “In time, I have come to realise that there are some incredible open source tools out there already which have been extensively developed, and that I do not need to reinvent the wheel. For example, [SourceCred](#), can be used to create a credit system based on GitHub work. The goal I wanted to achieve here is to demonstrate good scientific principles in reproducibility on GitHub as though it is a public portfolio for your work. Initially, I thought perhaps evidence of the way I work might be embedded in the words I use in our repositories. This year has been a learning curve, and the penny has finally dropped that embracing GitHub actions is probably the skill I need to learn to publicly demonstrate I can comply with reproducible research principles. That, and to make far more of the work I do public.”

The hope is that insights from this case study can be translated into actionable plans to impact positive behaviour and culture change across all levels of the organisation, to create the right incentives and support infrastructure, and encourage developers and project contributors to apply good working practices. GitHub data can also actively draw attention to colleagues successfully releasing their work to the public or engaging with external institutions. I feel that is the exact tool I have been looking for to complement our working culture.”

Challenges: just because you *can* do it...

Celebrating achievements by recognising different kinds of outputs in data science and AI can foster a positive work environment and sense of community, however, there are challenges, Joseph adds.

“It is important to acknowledge that not all work happens on GitHub, so there is an ethical consideration there. For some people, their work on GitHub may reflect a very small part of their role and therefore, might not be considered a fair reflection of their work. Furthermore, if we are considering tools, they will only be useful if they apply to the software we already use as an organisation. Project management for non-coding projects may be done through other software, technical operational support may happen through Azure DevOps, and data of a sensitive nature will not be shared internally within the entire organisation. At an organisational level, the external reputation of a research organisation is often tied to work such as technical reports, manuscripts and, typically, the underlying research data and associated code for reproducing the research.”

The EiRs in their AI/ML clinic also discussed the challenges associated with analysing unstructured data, such as the frequency of words associated with a GitHub repository, and how such analyses can be misleading and potentially harmful. Joseph adds: “Given the abundance of words on GitHub, the temptation was to use deeply flawed word counting or AI summary of the contents, and indeed that suggestion was not encouraged by the cohort. Words are complex, nuanced, laced with double meanings and have the potential to create fake patterns.”

There is also a risk that such methods – and metrics derived from those approaches – could be used intrusively or punitively. The Practitioners Hub EIR cohort understandably had ethical concerns based on the potential misuse of data and data analytics. “For the limited prototype I explored, it was not a technically challenging exercise,” says Joseph. “The real barriers to using GitHub data as an organisational performance indicator are ethical, and this is something I noticed the Turing Way guidebook has referred to as techno-solutionism. It is important that any technological solution, such as data? is used sensitively and does not create a culture of feeling policed. I have concluded that any kind of GitHub credit system didn’t quite fit right with me in nurturing the spirit of a digital community. The overwhelming success of any member of the community should not be to the detriment of their colleagues.”

Next steps: gauging opinion internally

Joseph states, “This work began with the goal of further embracing our digital community and celebrating positive developments and achievements demonstrated through our GitHub repositories.” While collaborative platforms like GitHub can foster a positive work culture, institutional platforms that aren’t designed for collaboration can conversely lead to siloed work, isolated teams, and a negative organisational culture.

There is also an equivalent capacity to use the data for malicious purposes. Joseph emphasises: “From what I have learnt at Cefas, uptake depends on whether it is enthusiastically embraced at the individual level, rather than being something applied to them, with people clearly able to see the benefits for their work. Consequently, our first action is to present what I’ve learned to our staff internally and invite feedback on whether GitHub actions training could influence work culture. The intention is to use the carrot rather than the stick, encouraging better practices at the user level so if someone is doing good work in the foundations of a project, they know it can be promoted and

celebrated.”

Key takeaways

- Technical platforms significantly influence work culture. Therefore, platform selection should prioritise fostering open and reproducible scientific practices.
- While data science and AI are rapidly transforming business and product development, other areas, like recruitment, are facing more challenges in a world of generative AI.
- Incentivisation approaches in the workplace are not usually considered when adopting data-driven strategies.
- Organisations possess a wealth of internal and public data that can inform decision-making, supporting both institutional goals and employee development.
- The same data, if not handled responsibly, can lead to misuse, misrepresentation, and flawed decisions, harming individuals and the organisation as a whole.
- Any AI tools or algorithms proposed must be community-driven and implemented with consideration of the potential for harm.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: Joseph Ribeiro

Joseph Ribeiro works at the Centre for Environment, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Science (CEFAS). At CEFAS, they provide scientifically evidenced advice on issues such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and food security, all of which are supported by marine monitoring data. The Research Vessel Cefas Endeavour collects biological, plankton, and acoustic data, as well as seafloor imagery. Joseph is a data scientist who sees opportunities to apply AI to assist tasks that currently require human effort and to develop new tools for acquiring novel data.

Practitioners Hub reflections/testimonial

Joseph says: “At Cefas, we often work on proof-of-concept AI projects or ideas which are often successful, but face challenges before the roll-out stage. I took part in the Practitioners Hub to gain exposure to organisations that do it from start to finish, or individuals whose role is based around the delivery of AI projects. I also wanted to get a deeper understanding of some of the concepts in The Turing Way handbook, particularly around AI and ethics, where there were lots of things I hadn’t previously considered. Although it may not seem obvious at first, some aspects of our work are analogous to the ethical concerns and biases we see with human-focused AI tools. For example, a poorly trained marine AI model may incorrectly identify less common species of fish, which could lead to unwanted outcomes such as overfishing.

We have worked closely with The Turing on adopting AI automation techniques into our Plankton Imager project, which monitors levels and species of plankton in the sea (zooplankton are small but incredibly important for carbon sequestration). We ended up having to reverse engineer some of the ethics and human-in-the-loop elements of that project – we can learn from the principles of the Practitioners Hub and The Turing Way by making sure AI ethics is built into projects and systems right from the start.”

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: turing-way@turing.ac.uk.

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